

New Life for All Nations Ministries

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Entry tags: Pentecostal, Religious Group, Language, English, Yoruba Language

New Life for all Nations Ministries is a product of a massive evangelistic push in villages, towns and cities in southwest Nigeria in the early to mid 1970s. The evangelistic work which produced the church was spearheaded by an itinerant preacher by the name, J.K Solomon. Evangelist Solomon had previously been a Police officer in the Nigerian Police Force. He however heeded the call to preach the gospel of Jesus Christ to all nations. He was supported by a band of young and enthusiastic evangelists in the evangelistic campaigns. Together, they travelled across major towns in western Nigeria to preach the gospel and disciple those who accepted their message. They then planted churches in these towns, leaving behind one or a few members of their team to help groom the converts. When members of the newly established church became stable in faith, they also began to launch out to their surroundings to evangelise and further expand the membership of the church. The church has its headquarters in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria from where its branches are coordinated for effective implementation of the church mandate. The vision of the church includes; 1. To take the gospel of Jesus Christ to every nation of the world 2. To plant New Testament churches in every nation and 3. To disciple the reached for the purpose of reaching un-reached. To fulfil its mandate, the church relies on members to engage in personal evangelism as it also organises and conducts mass evangelistic campaigns. It also engages the mass media, new media and other outlets to propagate the gospel. A number of other tools aside evangelism are deployed to ensure the church continues on the path of actualising its dreams. These tools include in-depth study of the scriptures, prayers and other fellowship programs. The church Mission and Pastoral Institute provides training for ministers and missionaries who are designated to lead church branches or those being sent out as missionaries to new or existing missions fields. As a means of fulfilling its vision the church holds annual conventions where members from the various branches come together in corporate fellowship to reinforce their collective beliefs and encourage one another unto the burden they all willingly bear. During such periods, the general congregation of the church engages in corporate mission outreach, workshops and specialised seminars which are all targeted towards renewing their resolve and engagement for evangelism (soul-winning). Constitutionally, the term of office of the President or General Overseer is tenured. They have succeeded in having peaceful transition from one leader to the other. The leaders claim that position is a privilege and so should not become a subject of quarrel or strive. They appear to be committed to fulfilling the evangelism mandate they set for themselves above the quest for occupying offices. As a result of their evangelistic drive, the church now has branches in many anglophone and francophone countries in West Africa, Europe and the Americas.

Date Range: 1972 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria, West Africa

Region tags: Nigeria, Africa

Nigeria, West Africa.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: <https://www.bible.com/ckb/languages/yor>

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.facebook.com/newlifefan/>

– Source 1 Description: New Life For All Nations Ministries Facebook page

– Source 2 URL: <http://Newlifefan.org/>

– Source 2 Description: New Life For All Nations Ministries website

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.kingjamesbibleonline.org/>

– Source 1 Description: The Authorised King James Version of the Holy Bible. Branches of the church make use of Bible translations in their local languages depending on the language spoken by the congregants of each local church

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: The group has its presence in and is heavily invested in Nigeria. Because Nigeria is a secular state with no state religion, various religious groups seek membership from within the population and this makes the cultural contact competitive.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Though there are moments of religious tension in some parts of the country, (especially the north) the religious atmosphere generally in the southern part of the country where the group is mostly domiciled is generally calm and accommodating

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Notes: The cultural contact among religious groups in Nigeria cannot be said to be overtly neutral.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: This is just a way of accommodating children born to members of the church until they have come of age to personally decide to become full members of the group.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Notes: The age at which each person chooses to become members is not fixed. It only takes an adult to decide at their time on becoming members of the group.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group is very active in proselytizing and recruiting new members as they make evangelism one of their cardinal programmes.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: Members of the church agree that it is a must for them to join in proselytising so as to min many to their fold.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

Notes: All members of the church agree that it is a must for them to join in proselytising so as to min many to their fold.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: A distinction should be drawn with respect to the mandate for missionary work among members of this group. While some are active being resident in the missions field, others actively support them in other ways. Some pay scheduled visit to those mission fields spending weeks or few months each year to support the work. Others send their resources to the field to aid the work of missions while they all pray for the success of the work both individually and

collectively in their meetings.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 200000

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 0.1

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The group believes in the authority of the Holy Bible.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Are they written:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Are they oral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: The stories associated with the origin of scriptures are those passed on from the time they were written. They include how Yahweh revealed himself to the prophets and the people who lived when the scriptures were written.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: The scriptures have been canonised and cannot be altered by anyone.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Is iconography present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: Their worship centres or meeting venues are considered sacred and holy. No one is expected to be involved in any activity considered offensive to the group in any space whatsoever, whether in their homes, workplaces, etc. However, they consider it a greater affront for anyone to subject their meeting venues to unacceptable practices.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that

some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the spirit and body are two distinct components of the human essence

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The group considers the spirit as the force which activates the body. Without the spirit, the body is as good as dead. Also they see the body as the engine for the spirit. Though the spirit may have a lot lined up to achieve, it can only do them through the agency of the body.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that the body and spirit are two distinct components of the human body.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Other spirit-body relationship:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that there is another life after the current dispensation. They hold that the life is split into two distinct types; the blissful and the painful.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: The group does not believe in reincarnation. They do not also perform special treatments on adherents' corpses.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: The group gives befitting burials to the corpses of the deceased members.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

As cenotaphs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: The family decides the tomb site for their deceased. When this is done, they contact the church to conduct the interment service in honour of the dead.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: The group thinks of the supreme high God as being possessing human attributes and characteristics. They ascribe to him such features as "the one with the mighty arms, one who makes the earth his footstool, one who constantly thinks about humans" etc.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: The group talks of the high god as one who dwells in the heavens.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: The group does not equate the supreme high god with any other being.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

Notes: The group sees every human including the monarch as the emanation of the high god. No individual enjoys this status exclusively to the exclusion of others.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the supreme high God is incontrovertibly good. They believe that in him is no evil whatsoever.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: The group conceives of the supreme high god as being omnipotent, omniscient, all loving, merciful, compassionate among several other good features.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

— Yes

Notes: Darkness is considered as light before him. The group accept the

position of the bible that nothing is hidden before the high god, not even the things done under the cover of darkness.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that the supreme high god knows the end of everything from the very beginning.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: The group believes that the supreme high god has all knowledge including those that are hidden from humans with him. He does not seek knowledge of events from an external body. They hold him as the custodian of all knowledge

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that everything in the universe emanates from the supreme

high god.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the supreme high god rewards all actions undertaken by members of the human family.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Notes: The supreme high god is seen as the just one who punishes the wrongs done by every being.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: The group sees the supreme high god as the one who either actively or passively brings to effect all actions and deeds on the planet.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: Though the description of the supreme high god as conceived by this group

suggests he is capable of positive emotions alone, however, he is also one who exhibits negative emotions as well. His negative emotions are always directed towards evil men and women. He does not afflict the good people with his negative emotions. His grand plan for the evil doers who suffer his negative emotions is to find the punishment as a corrective tool to bring them to repentance.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

Notes: The form of hunger associated with the supreme being by this group is that of apportioning rewards and punishments to those deserving of them.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: The group holds that all good features that can be conceived of are inherent in the supreme high god. They see him as all loving, all gracious, benevolent etc

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: He does this as prayers are offered to him by the group members.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: He is seen as one who also reaches out to humans through their

circumstances, through the scriptures, through the counsel of elders and more experienced folks etc

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: These includes angels and other heavenly creatures.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: They are not usually felt physically. However, they may be felt when they want humans to be aware of their presence.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Because they are ministers or agents in the theocratic administration of the supreme high god, they are seen to possess all the basic attributes of the high god whom they serve and are responsible to.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: They know the powers of the high god and are persuaded he will be victorious over the evil one in the last days.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: They derive their powers from the supreme being and work as they are

permitted to by the supreme high god.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Notes: When on a mission to perform a duty by the supreme being, they conduct themselves in a manner as to effectively achieve the purpose committed into their hands. If it is to avenge the wrong done by a being, they go all out to do so. They exhibit the kind of emotions needs (either positive or negative) to carry out the duty.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: They possess hunger to reward good deeds and punish unwholesome behaviours.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: They possess all emotions the supreme high god also possesses. They are helpful, kind, loving and compassionate among others.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Food:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Notes: For example, the group holds that human bodies are the temple of the living god. They therefore uphold the tenets of the scriptures which says anyone who uses their body for sexual sins, god will destroy such a fellow. They see the human body both as sacred spaces and sacred objects which cannot be desecrated without dire consequences.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: The group holds that supernatural beings care also about lies, cheating, dishonesty etc

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: The group holds that the supreme being cares about sexual activities with animals, with same sex partners, premarital sexual activities etc

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: The group holds that the supernatural beings are interested in every aspect of the

lives of all mortals. They derive pleasure in being involved in their daily activities and decisions.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that punishments meted for wrong doing could be served through various means including karma.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that punishments in the afterlife would be very extreme and severe.

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:
– Yes
Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria
- ↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE
Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

Notes: The group does not believe in reincarnation. However, it believes that those who inherit eternal life in heaven will take on an incorruptible life form.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

Notes: The group does not believe in reincarnation. However, it believes that those who religiously follow the way prescribed by the group will inherit eternal life in heaven. They conceive of life in heaven as a superior realm of existence.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that all humans will receive a just reward for their deeds or actions on earth. It therefore admonishes her members to act in manners that will make them qualify for pleasant rewards in this life

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

Notes: Though the group does not involve in physical battles as combatants. They believe that life itself is a battle ground. Success in the battle of life is therefore seen as rewards in this life.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Notes: The group believes that good health is a reward from the supreme being. They teach that when they heed the instructions of the supreme being, he tends to reward them with good health and sound mind.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that evil will be far away from those who are upright in this life.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: The group acknowledges Jesus the Christ as their messiah.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

Notes: The group has a clear idea about the whereabouts of their messiah. They hold that he is presently in heaven preparing a place for those who believe in him so he could give them a well deserved welcome at the eschaton. They however hold that his time of return is not known.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Alive, identified:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Coming in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Coming on specified date:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Coming has already passed:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that the messiah came to save men, reconciling them to God. He came to save the sinners and those lost in their ways.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Other purpose:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that it is the duty of the church to continue to evangelise the whole world. When each nation and tribe has been received the gospel, the world would come to an end.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

Notes: The church holds that the world will be judged by the supreme being and his Christ at the close of this dispensation

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Yes

Notes: This group believes that a new Jerusalem (world) would emerge at the end of the judgement of the world where there will be order and perfect peace. This city shall be under the full control of the supreme being.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– Yes

Notes: The system the group hopes for is one which shall be essentially religious but it shall have a political angle. The city shall be one where the praise and worship of the supreme being shall be heralded day and night. However, it shall be under the full control (politically) of the supreme being.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Notes: The group holds that those who are faithful and refuse to deny the Christ shall survive the eschaton.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ All religious in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ A subset of religion in-group members will survive the eschaton:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ All members of the sample region will survive the eschaton:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Everyone in the world will survive the eschaton:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Other survival condition:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Notes: The moral norms are exactly the same with the conventional norms of the group. There are no distinctions between the set standard and the practice of the in group members as far as morals are concerned.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ **Courage (in battle):**

– Yes

Notes: The group does not engage in physical battles, however, they hold that life itself is a battle. They therefore believe that humans must face life squarely and to make progress, those who are serious about life must fight hard to overcome all obstacles to their success.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ **Courage (generic):**

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ **Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:**

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ **Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:**

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ **Generosity / charity:**

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ **Selflessness / selfless giving:**

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Strength (physical):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– Yes

Notes: The group sees power as a phenomenon which must be approached carefully and handled with caution. The fact that an individual is in a position of power should make them sober, display the highest level of responsibility and accountability. The fact that a person has a high ranking status should also make them sober as nobility is not also a reason to malign or cheat others who do not have such privilege.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– Yes

Notes: The church acknowledges beauty and attractiveness but places more premium on the beauty of character and dignity above the physical beauty and attractiveness.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: The group advocates godliness, sincerity, sobriety, calmness of spirit and mind among other important virtues.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Other sexual constraints (males):

– Yes

Notes: The church frowns at men engaging in same sex marriage or mating with animals. It only allows heterosexual sexual relations.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: The church frowns at women engaging in same sex marriage or mating with animals. It only allows heterosexual sexual relations.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 12

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 80

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 48

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: The adherents live in communities provided with schools by the government and private investors in the educational system.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: The group's adherents interact with bureaucracies of government in Nigeria.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The government stores grains in large silos managed by the Federal Ministry of Agriculture in strategic locations across the country. The grains are released to the public to regulate prices of the commodities

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: This happens in certain regions of the country as public water management has collapsed in some areas within the country.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: This is mostly provided to all residents of the country by private investors in the transport industry.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Notes: The group encourages members to pay tithes to the church coffers. This is used mostly to pursue the group's objectives of evangelism and other needs of the group.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The government levies taxes on all taxable adults of the country.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group's adherents interact with the institutionalised Police Force of the country. They depend on the Police for protection and the enforcement of the law.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group submits itself to the institutionalised Judicial system of the country.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: Execution is only pronounced against capital offenses.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: Corporal punishments in some cases come with jail terms handed to convicted criminals by the law courts.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: Seizure of property can only be effected when a competent court of jurisdiction has found that such property has been acquired through fraudulent means or if such property are proceeds of crime.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They are subject to the legal codes of the country.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s)

other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They are protected by the nation's military and are free to join the military as personnel to protect the integrity of the nation's external territories.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The languages commonly used by members of the group include English language and the local languages spoken by members across various localities across the country.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group uses the Gregorian calendar in planning and executing their programmes.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Members of the group either engage in private subsistent farming at individual family levels or they buy their foods from markets around them,

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1970 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Nigeria